

ON THE SMARANDACHE UNIFORM SEQUENCES

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Abstract. Let t be a positive integer with $t > 1$. In this paper we give a necessary and sufficient condition for t to have the Smarandache uniform sequence.

Key words. Smarandache uniform sequence, decimal notation.

Let t be a positive integer with $t > 1$. If a sequence contains all multiples of t written with same digit in base 10, then it is called the Smarandache uniform sequence of t . In [2], Smith showed that such sequence may be empty for some t .

In this paper we give a necessary and sufficient condition for t to have the Smarandache uniform sequence. Clearly, the positive integer t can be expressed as

$$(1) \quad t = 2^a 5^b c,$$

where a, b are nonnegative integers, c is a positive integer satisfying $\gcd(10, c) = 1$. We prove the following result.

Theorem. t has the Smarandache uniform sequence if and only if

$$(2) \quad (a, b) = (0, 0), (1, 0), (2, 0), (3, 0), (0, 1).$$

Proof. Clearly, t has the Smarandache uniform sequence if and only if there exists a multiple m of t such that

$$(3) \quad m = dd\dots d, 1 \leq d \leq 9.$$

By (1) and (3), we get

$$(4) \quad ts=2^a5^bcs=m=d \frac{10^r-1}{10-1},$$

where r, s are positive integers. From (4), we obtain

$$(5) \quad 2^a5^b9cs=d(10^r-1).$$

Since $\gcd(2^a5^b, 10^r-1)=1$, we see from (5) that d is a multiple of 2^a5^b . Therefore, since $1 \leq d \leq 9$, we obtain the condition (2).

On the other hand, since $\gcd(10, 9c)=1$, by Fermat-Euler theorem (see [1, Theorem 72]), There exists a positive integer r such that 10^r-1 is a multiple of $9c$. Thus, if (2) holds, then t has Smarandache uniform sequence. The theorem is proved.

References

- [1] G.H.Hardy and E.M.Wright, An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1937.
- [2] S.Smith, A set of conjectures on Smarandache sequences, Smarandache Notions J. 11(2000), 86-92.

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